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About UP2030:

UP2030 is dedicated to aiding cities in achieving climate neutrality through enhanced urban planning and design. The project introduces the innovative 5UP approach to support city stakeholders and local authorities in integrating climate-neutral strategies into their everyday actions and long-term planning. Focused on promoting spatial justice and inclusive participation, UP2030 empowers communities and local governments to become agents of change, driving socio-technical transitions that enhance urban liveability and sustainability. The project's strategy aims to produce actionable insights and scalable solutions for urban environments, prioritizing resilience, equity, and sustainable urban development.

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Abstract	Compiles the conceptual basis, process, and activities to initiate and maintain engagement with local stakeholder ecosystems through Learning and Action Alliances (LAAs). Emphasises the importance of ensuring diversity in the stakeholder engagement process in the city pilots, as well as provides indications on this for cities and liaisons.			

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Executive summary

This document describes the stakeholder engagement strategy designed for the UP2030 project. This strategy will be operationalised with support of Learning and Action Alliances (hereafter, LAAs). LAAs operate at the city scale and are composed of stakeholders from a variety of backgrounds, fields and expertise with the common objective to contribute to the co-development of solutions supporting required transitions to meet climate neutrality targets and facilitate their local uptake. In other words, UP2030 will support cities in developing implementation roadmaps to customise and evolve a range of existing tools and approaches that contribute to climate neutrality. This will happen through stakeholder engagement and co-creation, firstly to ensure that solutions match local urban climate needs, as well as to increase buy-in and support for the further adoption of these tools by cities.

This document provides both a conceptual approach and practical implementation point of view for the development of a sustained engagement strategy in the project cities' LAAs.

The conceptual approach describes the overall strategy for stakeholder engagement, including the framing and contextualization of what stakeholder engagement and cross-fertilisation means in the context of UP2030 (see section 2). The latter section (section 2) explains the benefits cities can obtain from a sustained engagement within the context of co-creation of solutions.

The implementation strategy describes the methodology for stakeholder mapping and introduces the process designed for the elaboration of engagement roadmaps in the eleven UP2030 cities (see section 3). These roadmaps will detail what are the main engagement activities to be undertaken by each city and how these are connected (i.e., how the outcomes from each activity may feed other activities) and additionally will explore potential synergies to optimise resources and reduce stakeholder fatigue.

The information needed for conducting the stakeholder mapping was conveyed to the cities and City Liaisons (see milestone 04). The engagement roadmaps will be elaborated in the next few months once the first round of workshops has been finalised, and the matchmaking between cities' needs and UP2030 solutions is fully concluded. These engagement roadmaps will be produced with the support of a series of online meetings and are expected to be included in an upcoming update of this deliverable.

As further support to the project cities and City Liaisons, additional guidelines on the organisation of stakeholder engagement workshops are provided in Appendix 1.

Acronyms

Acronym	Full name
D	Deliverable
DoA	Description of Action
LAA(s)	Learning and Action Alliance(s)
MfC	Mapping for Change
RCities	Resilient Cities Network
TSPA	Thomas Stellmach Planning and Architecture
UCCRN	Urban Climate Change Research Network
WP(s)	Work package(s)

Section 1: Introduction

1.1 Purpose and Scope

The purpose of this document is to outline the stakeholder engagement plan for the UP2030 project. It provides an overview of the objectives, principles, and methods for engaging stakeholders in the project. The document aims to guide the city pilots in understanding why stakeholder engagement is important, how it can be effectively implemented, and the potential challenges that may arise.

The scope of this document covers three main sections: Introduction, Conceptual Basis, and Implementation Approach. The Introduction section introduces the purpose and scope and the structure of the document, while the Conceptual Basis section explores the importance of stakeholder engagement in addressing complex problems, such as decarbonization of cities. The Implementation Approach section outlines the steps and strategies envisioned for carrying out effective stakeholder engagement within the UP2030 project.

1.2 Document Structure

The sustained stakeholder engagement strategy is organised as follows:

- ❖ Section 1: Introduction
- ❖ Section 2: Conceptual and sound basis for stakeholder engagement and participation in UP2030, i.e., WHY do we engage.
- ❖ Section 3: Implementation approach:
 - Stakeholder Mapping, i.e., WHOM to engage;
 - Design of the Engagement roadmap, i.e., WHAT will be done;
 - Introduction to methods and approaches for stakeholder engagement i.e., HOW to engage.

Section 2: Conceptual basis

2.1 Changes in complex urban environments require stakeholders' involvement

The UP2030 project aims to contribute to the achievement of the objectives of the Mission for Climate Neutral and Smart Cities.

A core element to successfully roll-out local deep decarbonisation strategies lies in stakeholder engagement, which serves to enhance and maintain the long-term commitment of local policymakers and other solution providers towards systemic transformation. Communities can foster a sense of ownership, promote collaboration across sectors, ignite complementary initiatives, increase awareness, and strengthen capabilities by actively embracing inclusive stakeholder engagement [1]. Stakeholders also bring valuable expertise to the planning process and serve as "critical friends" during evaluation to ensure transparency and verifiability. This process facilitates the participation of traditionally marginalised groups in planning and ensures equitable consideration of the broader social and environmental advantages of addressing climate change [2].

The decarbonisation of the urban environment implies deep changes in various sectors (from mobility, to buildings, energy, etc.) with many and interdependent actors involved, therefore requiring transdisciplinary and multidisciplinary approaches. These sectors and actors often have different priorities, frame decisions based on their backgrounds, experiences, mandates, and societal positions, which can and will normally be very diverse [3]. Likewise, there is often limited knowledge exchange and communication among all these different actors, often even within the same city administration or organization. That is why bringing together the entire ecosystem of urban climate actors is crucial to accelerate change, considering their needs and taking advantage of the opportunities and co-benefits that it can bring.

Complex and dynamic challenges, such as a city's decarbonisation, therefore, require a system thinking and the use of integrated approaches that combine best available knowledge and tools. Science can support this endeavour by bringing in scientific knowledge and tools, but importantly also by means of developing innovative approaches that can help to connect different types of knowledge and stakeholders, which often have different values and perceptions, but are overall connected to the problems at stake [4, 5]. For instance, addressing cities' sustainability relies on a good understanding of the problem - not only from a technical point of view, but also from a social standpoint. Studies can provide insights about the underlying causes and offer a wide range of solutions. However, the course of action will only change if city actors are being listened to and their priorities and perceptions understood. It is through this knowledge sharing and exchange process that actors might be able to better understand the complexity of urban change and the different perspectives from other stakeholders, and ultimately explore joint pathways to overcome challenges.

2.2 Why is stakeholder engagement important?

Stakeholder engagement within the UP2030 project is essential for inclusive decision-making, collaboration, capacity building, knowledge sharing, communication, and policy alignment.

Engaging a wide range of stakeholders helps to build a collective understanding and commitment to achieving climate goals while integrating sustainable practices into day-to-day activities. Furthermore, sustained engagement throughout the course of a climate neutrality-related project is essential to achieve long-term impact, understand the needs of citizens, local organizations, and enterprises, maintain consistency and accountability, facilitate adaptability, and garner public awareness and support. It also allows for continuous improvement, collaboration, and responsiveness, ultimately leading to more effective and sustainable outcomes for a just transition.

Engagement plays a crucial role in understanding needs, visions, and opportunities for several reasons:

- ❖ Engaging with stakeholders allows for a deeper understanding of their perspectives, concerns, and aspirations, in order to align city development initiatives with the actual needs and desires of the community.
- ❖ Engagement enables the identification of untapped opportunities: innovative solutions, new partnerships, and previously unrecognised opportunities for sustainable and inclusive development [6].
- ❖ Engagement is essential for inclusive development because it ensures that the voices of all relevant stakeholders are heard and considered. Inclusive development aims to create equitable outcomes and address the needs and interests of marginalised or underrepresented groups by including them in decision-making processes [2].
- ❖ Engagement also fosters ownership and empowerment among stakeholders [7]. When individuals and communities are actively involved in shaping their own development, they become more invested in the outcomes and are more likely to contribute to the success and sustainability of initiatives.
- ❖ Promoting the dissemination of climate science and evidence highlighting the scientific consensus and the benefits of decarbonisation.
- ❖ Strengthening and sustaining local political will for long-term systems transformation by establishing effective relationships with diverse stakeholder groups and engaging in effective communication with the broader community, including the general public [8]

In summary, stakeholder engagement contributes to the goals of the City Pilots within the UP2030 project and the Mission on climate neutrality and smart cities by promoting collaborative decision-making, understanding local needs and priorities, fostering innovation, building partnerships, and ensuring political continuity, social equity and inclusion.

Through sustained stakeholder engagement, UP2030 aims to identify and analyse the needs, obstacles, and factors which need to be worked on to help cities on their path towards climate neutrality. This analysis will contribute to the collaborative development of a shared vision among the various stakeholders involved in the mission. Additionally, the project will further study the existing conditions of each city in terms of their social, economic, governance, and environmental systems.

Achieving the climate-neutrality goal presents the complexity of conflicts of interest among different sectors and the unintended consequences that sectoral policies might have on the other sectors. For instance, the difficulty in finding a harmonious mobility model that combines different speeds, pedestrians, cyclists, micro-mobility, and road traffic, the combination of the existence of green spaces and social expulsion due to gentrification associated with the improvement of the city, etc. Although participatory processes are increasing in overall terms, particularly in Europe, their successful application depends on the country, city, and the specific sector [9]. Planners and policymakers do not always communicate properly to citizens, and decisions are adopted without a careful assessment of most coherent and aligned solutions. Climate change science has progressed a lot in the understanding of these issues, but much of this knowledge is not shared or appropriately communicated for all audiences to understand it.

From the above, it is clear that other ways of (scientific) knowledge transfer to decision-making are needed [10]. Incorporating stakeholders' knowledge into urban planning practice can therefore help in bridging the so-called "science-policy gap" and generating and distributing number of benefits and opportunities [11, 12], among others:

- ❖ the cooperation and integration of different types of knowledge from multiple sources and perspectives improves people's ability, including scientists, to understand and manage complex, rapidly changing social-ecological systems;
- ❖ the exchange facilitates negotiation and mutual learning among stakeholders, reduces conflicts and engagement activities increase support and actor buy-in for decisions made;
- ❖ the inclusion of stakeholder engagement processes enhances the quality of the research by considering more comprehensive information inputs, and the impact of the research by helping to frame questions that are not just scientifically but also socially relevant. This becomes a great opportunity to land powerful scientific-technical tools in the different socioeconomic and political contexts in which problems are described;
- ❖ participatory processes have shown to have significant improvements in lifting institutional and technical capacities for Climate Change management;
- ❖ participatory processes contribute to raise awareness, increase the social impact of project results and/or to foster the establishment of collaborative communities in the territory among many others.

2.3 Why is stakeholder engagement sometimes not effective?

Despite the benefits that come from incorporating or enhancing stakeholder engagement into urban decarbonisation projects, many challenges will continue to exist to successfully overcome the science-policy gap. As Choi et al. [13] outlined, scientists and decision-makers often have different goals (e.g., advance science versus obtaining popular support), they search for different things (e.g., the truth using a rational model versus a compromise, using an intuitive model), they speak different languages (e.g., scientific language requires translation to be understood by non-scientist, versus decision-makers who speak their own language full of acronyms), and importantly, they require different timescales (i.e., research can take a very long time and end up suggesting more research is needed, versus decision-makers, which require instant answers and concrete, implementable solutions).

From the research perspective, there are specific problems that need to be overcome. Due to the popularity and “must have” request in mitigation and adaptation plans to have participatory processes, the actual practice has translated into many technicians and scientists embarking in the development of participatory processes without having much ‘hands-on’ experience. This is causing several emerging issues which can prevent addressing the science-policy gap. A further problem lies in stakeholders being considered as data providers, and engagement processes as data extraction initiatives. While stakeholders in some cases might also be experts and have access to relevant data, they are not always topical experts, and so their interest in engaging in a participatory process is not only to provide, but also to obtain something useful in exchange. Moreover, experts are sometimes getting paid for their participation while stakeholders, citizens and community members are generally expected to give up their time for free. A second frequent problem is that engagement is often understood as a one-way communication, e.g., presenting ideas and findings, instead of having a two-way communication. Finally, often projects and people in charge invest limited efforts in translating the resulting scientific findings (papers), enriched through the participatory process, into meaningful information, knowledge, or lifted capacities for project beneficiaries. These and other issues pose a big risk of running into the so-called “stakeholder fatigue”, where outcomes do not match the expectations of users, and drive demotivation to join future initiatives.

2.4 How is stakeholder engagement understood by UP2030?

One of the key objectives of UP2030 (see Specific Objective 2 in the Description of Action (DoA)) is to embrace co-creation approaches at the city level to customise tools and methods for the delivery of prototyping actions, i.e., using neighbourhood environments as a testbed, and inclusively involving all relevant local stakeholders.

From the above, it is crucial for the UP2030 project to have a good understanding of: i) what is/what is not a stakeholder and a participatory process; ii) clearly define and manage the expectations and efforts required from all the participants, and iii) have a clear understanding on what co-creation implies in the design and implementation of a participatory process.

To bear in mind before starting any engagement activity:

- ❖ *Data providers and stakeholders are DIFFERENT actors. An expert and data provider could be also a stakeholder, but a stakeholder is not necessarily a data provider and should not be treated as such.*
- ❖ *INFORMING stakeholders about research outcomes, goals, tools, is NOT equivalent to ENGAGING. The motivation to engage has to stem from the desire of the scientist to answer meaningful questions for stakeholders or support the development of a knowledge base that can increase the social impact of the project in addition to any scientific goal.*
- ❖ *The success of the overall strategy will largely rely upon the definition of a good engagement strategy: WHY we want to engage, for WHAT purpose, WHOM we need to engage, and HOW much will be required from stakeholders and WHAT will they get in return.*

Based on the above, the UP2030 stakeholder engagement proposal builds on three core ideas: **Co-creation**, **Cross-fertilization**, and **Capacity Building**.

Co-creation is at the core of the UP2030 project. It intends to identify climate change challenges in a collaborative manner, as well as the exploration of potential solutions. As described by Brugnach and Ingram (2012) [3], knowledge co-creation differs substantially from conventional knowledge production approaches (Table 1). Main differences stem from the way problems and solutions are identified as well as the types of knowledge and frames accepted.

Table 1: Comparative assessment of conventional knowledge production processes within academia versus co-creation processes. Source: Brugnach and Ingram (2012) [3].

Conventional knowledge production	Knowledge co-creation
Knowledge is an abstract body of statements	Knowledge is constructed through relational practices
Problem solved by processing information	Knowledge actively co-produced to solve a joint defined problem
Problem and solution independent	Solution situational, derived from shared problem definition
Solution imposed	Solution developed collectively
Only one valid frame accepted	Multiple frames accepted as valid
Ambiguity (i.e., discrepancies in meaning and interpretation that exists in relation to a particular issue) are resolved by imposing the valid frame (generally technical)	Ambiguity resolved by creating a connected frame that represents a shared view on the problem

By **cross-fertilization**, we refer to the exchange of knowledge to favour mutual learning between different actors. It builds upon the integration of the many types of knowledge that stakeholders and project partners bring to the table, including scientific, technical, social and tacit knowledge, to frame a wide and inclusive picture of existing challenges. This knowledge exchange might include technical and practical experiences (e.g., good and bad practices) and supports the co-creation process.

Different **capacity building** activities are foreseen in the scope of the project with the intention to lift technical and institutional capacities supporting climate neutrality.

With these three key principles at the core, UP2030 will use a co-creation approach to develop its models/tools and solutions, which will be tailored to the specific target groups in the pilot communities. The methodology will ensure that needs of all actors involved are considered and are reflected in the design. Continuous interaction with prospective end-users and stakeholder ecosystems through the LAAs will be aimed at, thus supporting an effective cross-fertilisation of knowledge. Capacity building will be transversal to the UP2030 project. This approach will enable a higher buy-in of the solutions and ensure the inclusion of useful features aligned with the perceptions and needs of the final users.

Section 3: Implementation Approach

For participatory processes to be effective in each of the different UP2030 pilot cities (Figure 1) a series of steps needs to be carefully designed:

- 1) set up of the LAAs;
- 2) identification of key stakeholders to be involved;
- 3) elaboration of a detailed plan of engagement activities (engagement roadmap) to be implemented; and
- 4) identification of the most suitable methods and means of implementing the proposed activities.

Figure 1: Location of UP2030 city pilots

3.1. Set up of the Learning and Action Alliances (LAAs)

LAAs are local living labs consisting of diverse stakeholders and typically involve a process of shared learning and action planning. As such, LAAs may be formed around specific issues or geographic areas whose ultimate goal is to achieve positive, sustainable change through collective action. This is essential for building mutual understanding and trust among stakeholders.

In the UP2030 project, the implementation of LAAs in cities is a core tool to foster the involvement of different stakeholders in the identification of key urban climate needs, while also ensuring that strategies and solutions co-developed help reach the targets of each city while addressing other complex social and environmental challenges.

LAAs recognize the importance of validating different knowledge and opinions in achieving their objectives. Through the establishment of an LAA, the project intends to provide a space for stakeholder collaboration and knowledge exchange and co-creation throughout the project lifetime and beyond to:

- ❖ Integrate different types of knowledge, i.e., technical, scientific, practical knowledge;
- ❖ Give the same voice to stakeholders with different perspectives and visions;
- ❖ Allow participants to contribute towards addressing complex problems through consensus solutions (through their own knowledge and experience);
- ❖ Provide a mechanism for two-way dialogue and sharing feedback with all stakeholders.

Therefore, in UP2030, LAAs are knowledge exchange and co-creation platforms intended to support the communication, coordination, innovation, and dialogue between city stakeholders at multiple levels. In doing so, LAAs help overcome common challenges in urban policy, such as silo thinking and acting. Each of the UP2030 pilot cities will have its own LAA, though exchange is planned across all of them to build bridges and share experiences (e.g., peer learning activities to be organised within T4.4 Cross-pilot exchange Community of Practice and Strategic Learning). The fundamental mission of the LAAs is therefore to act as platforms for sustained engagement beyond the four key workshops (Analysis, Vision, Action Upscale), thereby supporting the three core participatory principles of UP2030: Co-creation, Cross-fertilization and Capacity building.

Learning and Action Alliances (LAAs)

Description

The UP2030 Learning and Action Alliances (LAAs) are local communities of practice with a focus on **knowledge exchange and co-creation**. These social structures are intended to support the communication, coordination, innovation, and dialogue between stakeholders at multiple levels and overcoming silo thinking and acting. The fundamental mission of the LAAs is to act as platforms to support the core participatory principles of UP2030: co-production, cross-fertilization and capacity building.

Objectives

- **Sustained engagement strategy** to involve all relevant participants: public actors, private actors, users (civil society) and knowledge institutes;
- Provide an space and guidance towards co-creation in just transition pathways;
- Joint learning where there are no established experts - rather than a top-down transfer of knowledge;
- Cooperation and integration of different types of knowledge from multiple sources and perspectives, with an improved distribution of decision power and providing tools for feedback and iteration steps.

Challenges addressed

- Defining needs, ideating, prototyping, implementing and evaluating solutions to the problems defined
- Identifying and engaging vulnerable target groups
- Identifying and adopting innovative solutions for the complex socio-technical challenges at hand.

Partners involved

MfC, RCities, VUB, LIAISONS, CITIES, ICA

Expected impact

The exchanges within the LAA frame shall facilitate negotiation and mutual learning among stakeholders, thus reducing conflicts and increases support and actor buy-in for decisions made. In addition, these participatory activities will help to frame questions that are not just scientifically but also socially relevant, as well as to lift institutional and technical capacities. Moreover, they contribute to raise awareness, increase the social impact of project results. As a key outcome stemming out from the LAA action, the actors are expected to reach robust **'Partnership commitments' towards climate neutrality** in each UP2030 city.

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Figure 2: Summary of definitions and intentions of the Learning and Action Alliances (UP2030 Kick-off meeting poster)

LAAs will be implemented through physical and online engagement in various project activities (e.g., workshops, interviews, training, webinars, etc.).

To ensure effective action for each city LAA, the following activities need to be implemented:

- Management and communication (see section 3.2);
- Identification of actors to be involved in the LAA (section 3.3);
- Elaboration of an engagement roadmap - supporting the co-creation activities (section 3.4);
- Engagement strategy (section 3.5).

3.2 How to operate a LAA?

Generally, we understand the LAAs as an 'informal space' enabling a process of engagement where all participants are considered equally important and contributors to a process through different types of knowledge and experiences. Therefore, flexibility needs to be included as a central element of the LAA's operation.

However, there are also several formal aspects to be considered to ensure sustainability and effectiveness of the LAA in achieving its goals. This involves developing clear and concise terms of reference for the LAAs, including:

- ❖ Definition of what are the desired outcomes (i.e., vision - what are the goals the LAA aspires to achieve). The LAA will promote collaboration and cooperation between stakeholders working together towards a common specific aim.
- ❖ Roles and responsibilities of members (who is responsible for the management of the LAA, how and how often will the LAA convene?). These questions will be addressed through the elaboration of an engagement roadmap. In terms of responsibilities, participants should have a clear insight on what kind of engagement activities are intended, how much effort will be required on their parts, and what clear benefits or overall contributions are expected.
- ❖ Rules for decision-making (i.e., internal governance of the LAA). This is based on the identification of what decisions need to be taken and with whom and how.
- ❖ Communication to/with the stakeholders. The LAA manager is responsible for regularly informing the stakeholders about the progress and achievements of the LAA, and the next activities to be organised. Moreover, communication also needs to include feedback-collection mechanisms. A simple tool to ensure an adequate level of communication is the regular dissemination of newsletters, such as the one produced within WP6, including a space for gathering perceptions and suggestions from LAA participants.

By formalising the LAAs, participants can better understand their individual and collective responsibilities towards urban climate actions and be held accountable for their actions. This can ultimately lead to more successful outcomes in UP2030 and to the establishment of sustainable partnerships addressing the urban climate needs of cities.

To comply with ethical research requirements, each team needs to ensure that each stakeholder involved in any participatory activity signs an informed consent form in the local language in advance. Steps to mitigate this are included by design in the UP2030 project, where one of the partners specifically deals with ethical and legal issues which may arise from activities.

3.3 Stakeholder Mapping

As explained by Varvasovszky and Brugha [14], stakeholders can be defined as *“actors who have an interest in the issue under consideration, who are affected by it, or who could have an active or passive influence on the decision-making and implementation processes”*. In practice, this implies actors that are affected by a problem at stake and/or have the capacity to change the course of action in a given territory.

Conducting a well-prepared stakeholder mapping is therefore crucial, as it allows to determine the relevant parties that should be engaged and involved in the co-created decision-making process, as well as gaining an understanding of the interests and perspectives of each stakeholder. Among its various

benefits, the stakeholder analysis provides a comprehensive understanding of the individuals or groups that may be affected by a decision, their potential to influence the outcome, and their capacity to contribute to the development of probable solutions, establishing a decision-making framework, or implementing the selected alternatives. Neglecting essential stakeholder groups is possible if a structured stakeholder analysis is not performed, resulting in biased outcomes with incomplete backing for the decisions taken [15].

In this section, we provide Pilot Cities and City Liaisons with a systematic (yet flexible) methodology to map key stakeholders in each pilot (i.e., identification of stakeholders) and make an initial categorization of these stakeholders. The guidelines do not cover the potential identification of relationships between stakeholders.

The recommended approach towards mapping and categorising stakeholders is divided into three steps:

- 1) Drafting an initial list of stakeholders;
- 2) Ensuring diversity and a well-balanced representation of stakeholders;
- 3) Suitability assessment.

STEP 1: Drafting an initial list of stakeholders

Each city team should develop a preliminary list of potential stakeholder groups. For instance, by listing all relevant actors in the different domains that project partners know are connected to the problems at stake. This activity builds upon and elaborates further on the first list of stakeholders already identified in the UP2030 kick-off presentations and through workshop 1. Furthermore, there is an opportunity to collaborate with UCCRN, who are also mapping stakeholders.

Similarly, project partners can informally approach their contacts and apply the so-called snowball technique, used for stakeholder mapping that involves starting with a small group of stakeholders and then gradually expanding outwards to include additional stakeholders as you identify them. To this end, the initially identified stakeholders are asked to suggest others who should be approached and invited to participate in the project, and then repeat the process with the new stakeholders who are identified (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Simplified illustrations of stakeholder mapping using snowball technique

Finally, a complementary approach is to investigate the existence of already established stakeholder networks (e.g., from previous projects or community of practices within the region, etc.) by asking stakeholders about existing social structures.

Based on previous experiences (e.g., [Horizon 2020 REXUS](#) project [16]), for the creation of the initial list of stakeholders, it is suggested to make calls and visits in person in cases where a connection already exists, or if you simply have worked previously with these stakeholders. Additionally, the telephone/online call communication and in-person contact should be done when prospective stakeholders are seen as particularly important for the co-creation process. The search for additional stakeholders can be done through internet search, in order to have a long and complete first list of all relevant actors (public and non-public actors), scales (local, regional, national), and sectors (energy, environment). Some basic information about the project, the case study aims and objectives, and the intended participatory process should be forwarded to all the contacted stakeholders.

Table 2: Contacting stakeholders

When it comes to contacting stakeholders for a project or initiative, establishing effective communication is essential. Engaging and developing trust with stakeholders is crucial for gathering input, building relationships, and ensuring the success of your endeavour. Below, we propose some steps which can help in making contact, though it is essential to tailor this process to each local context and dynamic:

1. Identify the relevant stakeholders (e.g., decision-makers, policymakers, technical providers...) for the activity that you plan to carry out.
2. Once you have identified the stakeholders, gather their contact information through official websites, directories (such as an Excel sheet), or other reliable sources.
3. Craft a compelling message (email or letter) that:
 - a. introduces yourself and explains the purpose of your outreach: Clearly communicates your interest in discussing their expectations of using, e.g., the Neutrality Story Map tool in the project and how it aligns with their areas of interest or expertise. Highlight the potential benefits and relevance to their work.
 - b. explains the activity (workshop, interview or focus group format): Briefly outline the format of the activity, including the estimated time commitment and any relevant details. Assure them that their input is valuable and that their perspective will help inform the development and success of the project.
 - c. is personalised to each recipient by referencing specific achievements, projects, or initiatives that demonstrate your knowledge of their work and establish a connection. This demonstrates that you are genuinely interested in their input.
4. Follow-up and be patient: After sending your initial outreach, allow some time for the recipients to respond. If you do not hear back within a reasonable period, follow up with a polite reminder. Persistence and patience are key when trying to engage busy individuals.
5. Consider additional channels: If you are unable to reach the desired individuals directly, explore other channels for engagement. This may include attending public meetings or workshops related to climate or sustainability, participating in relevant community events, or reaching out to local environmental organisations that might have connections or insights on how to establish contact.

As a complement to this stakeholder mapping process, several UP2030 cities have already included a dedicated activity within their initial workshop on needs identification. This consisted in creating a visualisation of the available stakeholder map and asking workshop participants 'who is missing'.

STEP 2: Ensure diversity and well-balanced representation of all types of actors and sectors

Once STEP 1 has been completed, it must be assessed whether there is adequate representation from all relevant sectors and correct any important bias. In this regard, pilot partners need to ensure:

- ❖ A balanced representation of different sectors (i.e., transport, energy, buildings etc.)
- ❖ A balanced representation of the number of actors belonging to different urban climate sectors.
- ❖ A balanced representation of the type of actors (e.g., policymakers, public and private decision-makers, non-governmental and citizen organisations, academia, etc.).
- ❖ A balanced representation of all institutional and governance levels that are relevant to the issues at stake (e.g., national, regional, local).
- ❖ A balanced representation of gender and other protected characteristics such as disability action groups

For additional support, we provide a tentative list of types of actors, often connected to Climate Change problems.

- ❖ Decision-makers and policy-makers:
 - Housing sector, property business/market
 - Politicians and/or advisors
 - Municipal Administration and technical staff of the City Council departments: urban planning, transport and mobility, environmental, energy, social care, education, municipal housing etc.
 - Ministries / Directorates / Centres of transport, energy, the environment, regional development, finance, etc
- ❖ Economic actors:
 - Housing sector, property business/market.
 - Transport sector
 - Energy/water companies
 - Technology Suppliers
 - Educational institutions
 - Chamber of Commerce
 - Finance sector
- ❖ Researchers from City institutions, universities and research laboratories, private companies working on the topic, individual experts
- ❖ Non-governmental organisation (NGOs) related to climate change and environmental issues, or Associations and civil organisations for community involvement
- ❖ Local businesses – existing and potential
- ❖ Local citizens, in particular youth groups (including children), vulnerable and marginalised groups

In terms of the **number of stakeholders**, it should be noted that there is no optimum number. It is important to prioritise the quality and commitment of stakeholders over the number. We should engage actors from the different sectors mentioned above, who also adequately represent the diversity of types of actors. It is important to emphasise that a balance must be maintained in terms of sectoral representation in order to avoid sectors having an excessive predominance over others, unless the co-design and co-creation processes are focused on actions linked to a particular sector.

Depending on the level of commitment and availability, pilot teams could decide to have a **core and extended group** of stakeholders. Core members are those with a high interest in the problems at stake and enough time availability to engage in numerous activities. Meanwhile, the extended group can include a longer list and participate at different points in time but also constitute important beneficiaries of the project outcomes and outputs.

STEP 3: Suitability assessment of identified stakeholders

Once the list has been created and validated, it is recommended to map actors against two criteria: **influence** and **importance**. Influence is defined here as the capacity/power of an actor to solve or exacerbate the climate change challenges at stake. Importance relates to how the climate change challenges matter to the actor (i.e., is it in their interest to solve it? / is this problem a major issue for their business?). Practical tips:

- ❖ Add a short and brief description of **how each actor is connected to the problem** at stake (e.g., causing the problem, advocating for a solution, impacted by the problem caused by third parties, with capacity to manage/solve the problem, etc.).
- ❖ **Assess qualitatively the influence and interest** of each stakeholder (-, 0, +).
- ❖ **Categorise each stakeholder into one of the four levels of engagement** (Figure 4). Ideally, stakeholders invited to join the LAAs will be those having a high interest and/or influence (i.e., *key players*, *latent*, and *defenders*). *Apathetics*, although they might gain interest through the project, should be the less representative group. Nevertheless, it is worth noting that clusters do not remain static over time, and it should be expected that for a stakeholder it is possible to initially be *apathetic* and through the process become at least as *defender*. The clustering should be used by the project partners to make sure to have overall engagement with actors that have the interest and the capacity to influence a change.

Figure 3: Stakeholder engagement classification matrix regarding influence and interest criteria

An excel template has been created and shared with the Cities and Liaisons to support the development of this exercise. This is useful to start outlining the relative power of each stakeholder in relation to the others before starting the participatory process. It is worth noting that poor **management of power dynamics** is one of the major reasons for engagement failing to deliver outcomes. The methodological design followed should ensure that power dynamics are appropriately understood and managed (for instance through the insights of City Liaisons). For example, it may not be appropriate to invite all stakeholder groups at the same table at the same time. Every context will require a tailored approach so that stakeholders are able to provide inputs freely. This may mean that several activities will need to be organised to ensure a full and honest representation, or that the facilitators design activities which are able to mitigate potential challenges (e.g., strong facilitation, a special room layout etc.)

3.4 Design of the Engagement Roadmap

An Engagement Strategy is a plan that defines the goals, target audience, and overall approach to engagement. Within the overall Engagement Strategy, the Roadmap is a detailed tactical plan that breaks down a broader engagement strategy into specific tasks, timelines, and milestones for effective implementation. In other words, the Engagement Strategy provides the direction, while the Roadmap offers a path for execution. This execution will require the direct involvement of Cities and City Liaisons partners, as well as the support of RCities, MfC and ICA.

We envision a number of intertwined steps leading to the design of the engagement roadmap that comprise:

- 1) Selection of solutions: UP2030 is supporting the development of a broad range of innovative tools and methods covering several topics related to cities’ decarbonisation. Thus, it must be acknowledged that not all UP2030 tools and methods will be undertaken in all the cities with the same level of effort and depth. All this information will be collated into an Engagement Roadmap identifying the set of required actions for the co-development and implementation of the UP2030 tools/solutions in each City. The process of the initial selection of the tools will be informed by the results of the first set of workshops on i) the identification of needs and barriers; and ii) the co-

design of visions. These results will help Cities to start identifying the path they need to take towards preparing and financing projects that address local issues in a holistic manner.

- 2) Elicitation of participatory components: the process for developing and deploying the UP2030 solutions may require different levels of public participation, (i.e., Figure 5 shows the spectrum of public participation developed by the International Association of Public Participation - IAP2).

Each solution may require different levels of participation by the LAA actors in its various stages of development. In this step, a survey will be conducted with the solution providers, accompanied when needed by a follow-up interview. It will be asked to list all planned activities for which any type of stakeholder engagement is needed, as well as to provide a brief summary of the main goal, expected outcomes, and proposed means of implementation (e.g., interview, workshop, survey, etc.) for these engagement activities. This will allow us to map what are the participatory components required for the application of each solution as well as the intensity of each activity in terms of level of participation from the stakeholders.

		INCREASING IMPACT ON THE DECISION				
		INFORM	CONSULT	INVOLVE	COLLABORATE	EMPOWER
PUBLIC PARTICIPATION GOAL		To provide the public with balanced and objective information to assist them in understanding the problem, alternatives, opportunities and/or solutions.	To obtain public feedback on analysis, alternatives and/or decisions.	To work directly with the public throughout the process to ensure that public concerns and aspirations are consistently understood and considered.	To partner with the public in each aspect of the decision including the development of alternatives and the identification of the preferred solution.	To place final decision making in the hands of the public.
	PROMISE TO THE PUBLIC	We will keep you informed.	We will keep you informed, listen to and acknowledge concerns and aspirations, and provide feedback on how public input influenced the decision.	We will work with you to ensure that your concerns and aspirations are directly reflected in the alternatives developed and provide feedback on how public input influenced the decision.	We will look to you for advice and innovation in formulating solutions and incorporate your advice and recommendations into the decisions to the maximum extent possible.	We will implement what you decide.

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Figure 4: Levels of stakeholder participation Source: IAP2

- 3) **All the information** collected through the previous steps **will be organised in a customised Miro whiteboard** (one board per LAA). This board will contain two exercises that can help to structure the collated information into a clear Roadmap of engagement activities.

As part of the exercise, engagement activities will be clustered according to their purpose, correspondence of the proposed methods, and foreseen timeline for implementation. This grouping will facilitate LAA leaders to get a clear overview of the types of engagement activities

foreseen in the different City pilots during the project, possible formats and timing, thus facilitating the planning for their design and implementation.

Within the UP2030 project, different types of engagement activities with stakeholders have been envisioned. Stakeholder engagement has been envisioned to take place through four key workshops but, depending on the time required to gather information in the pilot cities, the required inputs and validation of outcomes for the implementation of the project, the number of workshops and other engagement activities can be extended. This has already happened in several of the pilot cities for workshop 1, as this single engagement wasn't enough to collect the required information.

The first workshop will include a project presentation and will be the official kick-off for each City LAA.

A number of additional engagement activities will be organised in between the workshops - to be defined according to the needs and demands from each City (see Figure 6).

Figure 5: Roadmap for engagement activities – starting point

A series of 2 working sessions (to be extended if needed) will be scheduled with Cities and City Liaison partners managing each LAA. In these sessions, we will work together and go through the Miro exercises to move from the mapping of participatory components of the tools and methods to be implemented in each City Pilot into an engagement roadmap. In this roadmap, we will identify synergies between potential engagement activities (i.e., to avoid stakeholder fatigue) and will identify how the outputs from each activity will feed to other project activities.

3.5 Introduction to methods and approaches for stakeholder engagement

The Engagement Roadmap in UP2030 will be the backbone of the engagement activities that will be carried out in the City LAAs. The successful implementation of this roadmap requires embedding this engagement roadmap into a more comprehensive engagement strategy.

In general, the engagement strategy for UP2030 Cities should include three elements:

- i) the LAA **engagement roadmap**;
- ii) a simple **communication strategy** that identifies how and how often will the information related to the LAA activity be conveyed to its members, and through which channels; and how any potential feedback will be collected;
- iii) a map of the engagement methods to be used in each participatory activity. In this case, a key element is the identification of training needs of the team facilitating each participatory activity and who will need to use the selected engagement methods. To this end, an **Engagement Toolkit** for Cities and City Liaisons is currently being developed by MfC, TSPA and ICA.

In terms of engagement methods, there are a myriad of well-tested methods that can be used to support participatory processes (see e.g., '[The Multi-stakeholder Partnerships Tool Guide](#)' developed by [Wageningen University & Research](#) or the [catalogue](#) produced by the EU-funded [Engage2020 project](#)). In UP2030, we will prepare specific engagement plans targeting the needs and taking into account the potential barriers from each City. To facilitate the identification of engagement tools within the context of UP2030, these are divided into five broad categories:

- 1) Connection tools: to help to break the ice (when stakeholders are not yet familiar with each other) and let the stakeholder group to know each other and understand why everyone has been invited to participate. These can be useful to animate broader participatory activities.
- 2) Methods supporting an initial identification of needs and barriers (mostly related to Workshop#1). *Examples: Problem Tree; Web Forum Engagement; Surveys; Sensory Walk; Rapid Appraisal Participatory GIS; Spatial Assessment Workshop; Fuzzy Cognitive Mapping.*
- 3) Methods supporting the definition of shared visions representing both structural and intangible interventions comprising transformational pathways (mostly related to Workshop#2). *Examples: Proto-typing Solutions; Theory of Change Workshop; Arts Competition; Participatory Future Workshop; Future Newspaper.*
- 4) Action tools, that will include divergence tools, (i.e., to help a group acknowledge how they can perceive an issue from many different points of view) and co-creation tools focusing on the integration of different types of knowledge. These methods will be mostly used to support engagement activities in Workshop#3. *Examples: World Café / Pro-Action Café; Six Thinking Hats; Charrettes; Distributed Dialogue; Fish Bowl.*
- 5) Commitment tools: to help create a consensus for the selection of the most promising ideas or options and to assess what needs to be done to adapt or upscale these activities to other contexts. In our case, these will focus on supporting the elaboration of the UP2030 Partnership Agreements.

Examples: Partnership Agreements; Card Clustering; Closing Circle; Green Participatory Budgeting; Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis.

Several options will be provided as key stakeholder engagement methods. The final selection of engagement methods will be undertaken once we have clearly defined what are the key needs for the implementation of the engagement roadmaps in each UP2030 City.

Section 4: Conclusions and next steps

Initiating and sustaining a pro-active and well-thought stakeholder engagement process will be essential to make sure that the UP2030 project achieves its goals. Focusing on the principles of co-creation, cross-fertilization and capacity-building, LAA activities will be key to ensure the activation of diverse local stakeholder ecosystems.

At the time of writing of this deliverable, most cities have uploaded the results of their first engagement activity, which was workshop 1 on the identification of needs. Efforts are currently focused on reviewing these reports to provide a more bespoke approach to each city and City Liaison for further engagement, such as the set-up of the LAAs.

Over the next weeks, project partners working on engagement activities within the UP2030 project, such as the Stakeholder Engagement Toolbox, which is being developed by TSPA and MfC, or the description and classification of engagement tools led by TU Delft, will consolidate efforts through an Engagement Taskforce. The key goals of the Engagement Taskforce will be to devise and operationalise an Engagement Taskforce and its connected Roadmap.

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Appendix 1: Practical guidelines for designing and implementing workshops

Workshops are a valuable tool for stakeholder engagement since they can help to improve the increased engagement and motivation, mutual learning, improved problem-solving and enhanced collaboration, by providing a space for stakeholders to share their different perspectives, experiences, and knowledge. In UP2030, workshops are the central elements in our participatory approach in order to contribute to the delivery of the expected outcomes and impacts in each LAA.

The organisation of these events requires time and resource intensive dedication, and opportunities to engage with the full group of stakeholders are limited. Therefore, designing and implementing workshops requires careful planning and consideration of various factors, such as the goals of the workshop, the composition of the stakeholder group, and the facilitation and communication strategies employed. In this context, these guidelines for designing and implementing workshops can be helpful in ensuring that workshops are well-planned, properly-designed, well-executed, and contribute to meaningful stakeholder engagement, offering many benefits, both for the facilitator and the participants.

The organisation and conduction of these engagement processes with stakeholders should follow a series of key principles.

1. Objectives should be clearly stated;
2. There should be a broad range of interested parties/individuals and the diversity of participants should be ensured through, for instance, child-friendly sessions for parents/carers, or accessible spaces for disabilities or that have no religious connection;
3. Methods should be adapted to the local cultural/institutional/context;
4. Transparency in using the information: it is key to make clear how stakeholders' views will be used and what the information resulting from the workshop will serve for;
5. Allocate sufficient time to carry out the activities without overloading the participants. Some time for breaks and networking is necessary and helps create connection and engagement between the participants;
6. Stakeholders should receive intermediate feedback and a summary of results and conclusions from their contributions during the course of the process;
7. The results of the process should have an impact on the decision to be made or the process in which they are to be involved;
8. We should search for evidence of enhanced stakeholder understanding – i.e., social learning.

Having these keys in mind, structuring the organisation of stakeholder engagement participatory processes can be done in a series of sequential steps (see Figure A1.1) guided by a previous strategic reflection on the vision and goals for the pilot (Step 0).

Figure A1.1: Roadmap for workshops design and implementation

These steps describe the methodological backbone and logic to develop a coherent and fruitful participatory workshop or session, as well as the elements and aspects to be prepared and taken into account. A more detailed explanation for each of the recommended steps is hereafter provided.

A1.1. Pre-Workshop Phase

This is the preparation stage where the workshop organisers plan and coordinate the workshop activities. During this phase, the organisers set the goals and objectives of the workshop, identify the target audience, create the workshop agenda and materials, and promote the workshop to potential attendees. The pre-workshop phase also involves logistical arrangements such as venue booking, catering, and equipment setup.

STEP 0: Engagement Plan

As a first step, City Liaisons and City partners need to get a clear vision about where the City wants to go (i.e., what are the advancements that would like to be achieved) and what to get out of the UP2030 engagement process. This will be a core information in the overall engagement strategy of each City LAA.

Once this is clear, Cities can start drafting an overall planning of activities and associated timeline and start designing and planning each workshop (see steps 1-6).

STEP 1: Goals and objectives of the workshop

It is important to establish the definition of the primary and secondary objectives of the workshop. Moreover, for each of the workshops, Cities and City Liaisons will need to think in more detail about the objectives that should be achieved through the planned engagement activities. The following questions can help identify both categories' objectives.

- ❖ *What do we need to get (outcomes) from the participation process: information (quantitative, qualitative, perceptions, awareness...?)*
- ❖ *In which format do we need the information: numbers, causal relations, concrete data, general knowledge, perceptions, spatial representations...?*
- ❖ *Are we seeking any additional effects besides our main inputs: e.g. building sense of community, raising awareness, promoting networking and communication between the actors, foster/show transparency, educating on something/disseminate information...?*

The Box 2 provides a generic example of goals and objectives for a UP2030 workshop in a pilot.

Box 2. Example of goals and objectives for a series of UP2030 workshops in a City pilot

GOAL: (EXAMPLE) Build a common understanding about Climate Change and neutrality challenges

OBJECTIVES: (EXAMPLE)

- Identify the priority needs from stakeholder perspective in each City pilot;
- Develop a system's mapping on UP2030 barriers and opportunities;
- Present, discuss and validate the City pilot baseline assessment;
- Define the goals and aspirations of the LAAs in the Use Case.

STEP 2: Target audience and stakeholders

A key part in the design of a successful workshop is ensuring a balanced representation of all interested or relevant groups (unless the workshop's objective is especially focused on one or two specific groups), having a good knowledge of the actors engaged and the role of the different institutions they represent. Furthermore, it is key to acknowledge the level of understanding of the topics in each city - e.g., Granollers participants were not as informed as expected, resulting in poorer outputs than expected.

The preliminary analysis of the stakeholders should consider two key points:

- I. understanding in which way they can contribute to each of the planned activities (based on their experience and role) and;
- II. what are the added-value and benefits they can get from their participation in the workshop.

Moreover, the organisers should also be aware of existing dynamics between stakeholders. This is particularly relevant if there are ongoing tensions/conflicts between stakeholders that may limit or even impede a proper development of the planned activities. These conflictive dynamics need to be carefully considered as part of the design of the workshop.

Based on the results from the stakeholder mapping exercise, the organising team (Cities and City Liaisons) will produce a list of stakeholders to be invited to the workshop. It is important to make sure that there is a good balance in type of actor and institutional and governance levels.

STEP 3: Setting the methodologies

Depending on the type of outcome and the format required, a different methodology or set of methodologies will be more convenient. Once the methodology has been selected, the most logical and efficient sequence of steps should be defined, optimising time and resources while ensuring the achievement of results.

In this phase, workshop organisers need to start shaping the activities to be conducted, ensuring these are well aligned with the specific objectives. In order to achieve this, a number of points shall be adequately addressed, namely:

- ❖ List all project activities that will be included in the workshop series (this information will be included within the engagement roadmap for UP2030 Cities);
- ❖ Identify the methods/tools that are required/suitable for each activity (in conjunction with other UP2030 partners);
- ❖ Brainstorm on the best way to ensure a good and logical flow for the workshop;
- ❖ Define the workshop duration and format (also considering potential constraints, such as availability of key stakeholders);
- ❖ Define who will be participating from the project team and doing what.

STEP 4: Workshop planning and design

This step directly builds on Step 3 by operationalizing the initial design into the following specific actions:

Workshop design

It involves the following actions:

- ❖ **Defining the agenda and preparing a dissemination and an internal working agenda.**
Recommendation: allocate sufficient time to carry out the activities without overloading the participants. Some time for breaks and networking is necessary and helps create connection and engagement between the participants.

- Dissemination agenda: should include the title, location and main schedule of the workshop activities that meets the objectives. It is aimed for sharing with the participants to provide them with the essential information and attract their interest.
 - Internal working agenda: it should contain the same items as the external agenda, completed with the distribution of tasks among the organising team (person in charge) and the preparation details, as a sort of a script for the organisation and conduction of the workshop. Possible tasks include overall moderation, facilitation of groups, note-taking, generation of visual material (pictures, videos), etc.
- ❖ Ensuring the workshop's agenda runs smoothly.
 - ❖ Drafting a concept note (short document stating what the workshop is about, expected results, and target audience).
 - ❖ Preparing a facilitation plan (internal document describing details of who does what, how and when).
 - ❖ Organising a rehearsal schedule, bearing in mind that an internal rehearsal is often a key activity to ensure a proper development of the workshop. The team should carry out a full rehearsal of the workshop to make sure the exercises can be done within the allocated time, to foresee any possible unexpected situations (questions, polemics) and prepare responses, and make the organising team get hold of their tasks.

Material and resources needed for the workshop

Once the methodology is selected, including the design of exercises and dynamics, a list of required materials and resources should be prepared to ensure everything needed can be available. If some critical element cannot be accessed, an alternative should be searched for (alternative material, adapted exercise or an alternative method). Examples of valuable materials are Powerpoint Presentations, postcards, board charts, blackboards, stickers, etc.

Moreover, prior to the workshop, the organising team needs to take care of

- i) logistics (location of the workshop and booking of the place) and identification of required resources (e.g., catering and lunch, technical resources, accreditation tags, materials needed for the workshop);
- ii) sending out the invitations to the participants via email and making any personal contacts (by phone or in-person) for those stakeholders potentially more difficult to reach via email;
- iii) asking for confirmation of assistance and send reminders when the event gets closer. Some additional phone calls may help get further responses if the response rate has been low;
- iv) preparing attendance list and informed consent forms (see Appendix 1), including explicit consent for the use of videos and pictures from the workshop as UP2030 communication material, as well as possible sharing of email among participants;

v) strongly considering the hiring of a professional facilitator to support the workshop in case the organising team is not very experienced in conducting this kind of events; vi) organise and manage the reimbursement of travel costs, if applicable;

vii) preparing accreditation tags;

viii) elaborating an evaluation form or surveys to distribute online or printed during the workshop or through an evaluation email submitted one or two days after the workshop. Generally, any feedback gathering method onsite will gather more responses than ex-post via email. Undertaking some kind of process evaluation is important in order to assess: 1) the quality of the process, 2) the satisfaction of participants / suggestions for improvement, 3) to gather additional individual-based information or feedback, 4) assess the perception of usefulness, learning from the process;

ix) sending out any resources that might help the participants learn about the topic(s) beforehand so all participants are up to speed and can contribute to the discussions

Pilot Test

Carry out a rehearsal of the workshop to make sure the exercises can be done within the allocated time, to foresee any possible unexpected situations (questions, polemics), prepare responses, and make the organising team get hold of their tasks. Make any adjustments as required.

A1.2. Workshop phase

This is the actual workshop or training session where the attendees participate in the activities planned by the organisers. During this phase, the facilitator delivers the workshop content and engages the attendees through presentations, interactive discussions, group activities, and exercises. The workshop phase is the core part of the training where the attendees learn new skills and knowledge.

STEP 5: Running the workshop

At the workshop: the organising team needs to take care of taking notes, recording the session etc.

- ❖ Preparing the logistics and technology requirements, ensuring all workshop materials are ready to use, and conducting a dry-run and testing equipment;
- ❖ Establishing a clear communication plan: From the beginning, the main facilitator needs to make sure that there is a clear communication to all participants about:
 - WHY the workshop is undertaken (outlining the objectives in the frame of UP2030 and beyond);
 - WHAT will be done (clear agenda of the engagement activities that are going to be carried out);
 - WHAT are the expected outcomes (highlighting the expected benefits for all parties).
- ❖ Drafting an attendance list;

- ❖ Facilitating the workshop: during the workshop a key action is to appropriately monitor dynamics between the stakeholders, i.e., by making sure that:
 - All stakeholders are actively participating in the workshop activities, i.e., everyone has a voice;
 - Power dynamics are adequately managed and there is a good participatory environment where different types of knowledge can be integrated;
 - All participants correctly understand at all times what is being done and why this is being done, i.e., nobody gets lost.

- ❖ Managing the unexpected and adapting to changes.

Then, at the end of the workshop the participants will be asked to fill in the evaluation form (or email survey) and next steps will be presented as means to keep all participants engaged in future activities.

A1.3. Post-workshop phase

This is the follow-up stage where the participants apply what they have learned in the workshop to their work or personal life. The post-workshop phase involves evaluating the effectiveness of the workshop, gathering feedback from attendees, and assessing the impact of the training on the attendees' skills and performance. The post-workshop phase also includes providing support and resources to help attendees continue to develop their skills and knowledge after the workshop.

STEP 6: Workshop reporting and follow-up

There are several post-workshop tasks to be implemented, namely:

- ❖ Follow-up with participants and stakeholders:
 - Send a thank you email to the attendees, expressing gratitude for their attendance, contributions, and commitment to the cause of climate change mitigation and net-zero. Emphasise the importance of their continued involvement and highlight the next steps.
 - In case evaluation forms have not been provided on paper during the workshop, reach out to participants individually via email to gather their insights on the workshop experience through the evaluation form/survey on stakeholders' satisfaction and feedback to identify lessons learnt, gaps and room for improvements.
 - Prepare a workshop summary document that highlights the outcomes, the results and conclusions achieved in the workshop, and disseminate it among participants in 2 or 3 weeks after the workshop and another final summary by the end of the project.
 - Optional: Include any presentations, materials, or resources used during the workshop and make them accessible to all participants and stakeholders.
 - Identify and prioritise the action Points that emerged during the workshop, assign responsibilities and create a timeline for each action point and share this information with the relevant stakeholders to ensure clarity and accountability.

- Establish a communication plan to: a) Provide regular updates on the progress made towards the identified action points to the stakeholders, b) Determine the frequency and format of updates (e.g., email newsletters, virtual meetings, progress reports) based on the preferences of the participants and stakeholders.
 - Facilitate networking opportunities among participants and stakeholders to foster collaboration and knowledge sharing: Arrange meetings, webinars, or conferences where individuals can connect, exchange ideas, and explore potential partnerships or collaborations.
 - Establish a plan for future workshops and events that build upon the discussions and outcomes of the initial workshop.
 - Share information about upcoming events and encourage participants and stakeholders to participate and continue their engagement.
- ❖ Gather and digitalize the information co-produced with stakeholders during the workshop.
 - ❖ Analyse the information and turn it into usable results for the project/process' aims. Draw out a few conclusions of the session.
 - ❖ Make sure you comply with EU regulation on data protection, i.e., GDPR rules (as stated by the UP2030 ethical requirements).
 - ❖ Proceed to the reimbursement of travel expenses or compensation for time if applicable.
 - ❖ Make the report (or a version of it) publicly available, preferably by publishing relevant information using the social media and website of the UP2030 project.

Beyond these steps, there are several guiding principles that need to be considered for a successful and impactful organisation of a workshop, which are summarised in section A1.4.

In addition, Box 3 below shows, as an example, some recommendations after the evaluation of the results and perceptions of the Use Case workshop in Granollers, carried out on 29 March 2023:

Box 3. Recommendations to take into consideration for future workshops in Granollers (- internal reflection after the first UP2030 workshop)

- Prepare Pre-Workshop Materials: Provide participants with relevant pre-workshop materials to ensure a common understanding of the vision and related concepts of climate change adaptation and mitigation. This can include background information, case studies, research papers, or relevant reports.
- Facilitate resources for further learning and development, depending of the type of the stakeholder
- Evaluate the effectiveness of the previous workshop by collecting feedback from participants and stakeholders. Identify areas that worked well and those that need improvement.

- Clearly define the workshop's purpose and its expected outcomes. Ensure that the vision for the workshop is well-defined and communicated to participants and stakeholders prior to the next workshop.
- Set specific objectives: Define specific objectives for the workshop, outlining what you aim to achieve. These objectives should be measurable, achievable, relevant, and time-bound (SMART).
- Tailor the agenda one month in advance: Design an agenda that is structured, balanced, and engaging. Consider incorporating a mix of presentations,
- Interactive sessions, group activities, role-playing, breakout sessions and discussions are encouraged in such workshops to foster stakeholder participation and collaboration.
- Invite diverse participants instead of only one type of stakeholder, though being careful about potential power dynamics (e.g., topic experts may 'intimidate' less informed stakeholders, whose views are equally as important): Encourage networking and collaboration among participants. Design activities that promote teamwork and the exchange of ideas. Provide platforms for participants to connect and continue discussions beyond the workshop.

A1.4. Final recommendations and conclusions

Final specific key points or recommendations to ensure the success of a participatory workshop or session include the following:

- Make sure to explain very well the objective of the workshop and how it fits within the broader project, and if there will be future follow up/next phase sessions;
- Manage and balance expectations (i.e., make sure to explain very well the objective of the workshop, how the inputs from the participants will be included, what the role of the participants is and what the full group can get from the planned exercises);
- Explain carefully what the role of the participants is and what they will be asked to do during the session;
- Continuous Engagement:
 - Maintain regular communication with participants and stakeholders through newsletters, social media updates, or an online platform dedicated to climate change mitigation;
 - Provide information that may be useful/interesting for the participants: relevant news, research findings, and success stories to keep everyone informed and motivated
- Ensure a good moderation so all the participants feel equally encouraged to contribute and there is an atmosphere of respect, order, and equality;
- Try to integrate the stakeholders' interests in the discussion topics/exercises to ensure a balance between their concerns and needs and the specific objectives of the process;

- Meeting should be fun and engaging;
- Simplicity is appreciated;
- Good planning and facilitation is key;
- Make sure that stakeholders end up with a feeling that their opinions have been listened to and taken into account.